

Development of an analytical framework to improve understanding and assist in operationalizing NC valuation

Project JHI-D5-1 “Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital Valuation” - Deliverable D2.1

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Abstract

This report presents an analytical framework developed to investigate place-based monetary and non-monetary values as a lever to inform decision-making at landscape scale. The framework combines the information extracted from an extensive review of the literature on the knowledge of values and natural capital (NC) valuation, co-constructed with relevant stakeholders. The framework shows how stakeholders' input can be obtained through a series of workshops that use a novel combination of participatory-based techniques focused on scenario-building and elicit current understanding of diverse values for nature in Scotland, as well as how these may develop in the future under a range of drivers. The framework, which is in line with suggestions provided by the IPBES (2022), Pasqual et al (2023) and others (Nijnik and Miller, 2017), emphasises the importance of building relationships i) among diverse stakeholders involved in managing NC at landscape scale, including local communities, and ii) between the community of practice (Metzger et al., 2019), including policy makers, and researchers, as well as iii) the necessity to facilitate the integration of traditional economic methods for valuing NC and ecosystem services (ES), with less often utilised participatory techniques. A reconciliation between economic and cultural aspects of NC, as proposed by the "triple balance sheet" (Turner, 2016), is considered to account for incommensurable values in decision-making (e.g., values that cannot be reduced to common measures such as liberty, equality, feeling part of nature) and thus encourages win-win strategies for NC governance through deliberation of contested issues. The framework can be relevant for different audiences, and used by academics and practitioners operating in decision and policy making to:

- Explore NC values through stakeholder engagement.
- Investigate drivers of change that influence the condition and values of NC, through scenario development.
- Suggest how to apply these scenarios to a specific geographical context, investigated by participatory mapping, to inform ecological, economic, and social values (all potentially explorable using a mixed-method toolset).
- Reconcile incommensurable values through deliberative analysis to reduce contestation and formulate win-win strategies for managing NC sustainably.
- Identify policy-relevant issues related to the management of NC and embed NC into policies.

Key message

The framework suggested in this report depicts human-nature relationships to address implications for local-level wellbeing. It can underpin decision making at a landscape scale, and, we believe, can be used to inform policy analysis at higher level (e.g. by guiding the formulation of new policy goals), to highlight needs for regulatory and economic instruments (e.g., taxes, compensation payment) or to suggest a set of biophysical, economic, and cultural indicators to measure the success of the policy already implemented.

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Introduction

This report is the Deliverable D.2.1 “*Development of an analytical framework to improve understanding and assist in operationalizing NC valuation*” of the project JHI-D5-1 “*Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital Valuation*”. The framework is proposed to advance knowledge of integrated valuation through a mixed methods approach (with a participatory based toolset scaled to the availability of data, to be developed in D.2.2) that accommodates different types of values assessed using diverse information sources and techniques. It is expected that this may facilitate knowledge exchange, stakeholders’ engagement, and awareness-raising to inform decision making in the Scottish forest context.

The approach adopted builds on and refines consolidated methods of valuation proposed by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2022) based on direct observation (e.g. spatial ES mapping); statement based-valuation (which gathers information from individuals on their pre-formed preferences or those co-constructed through deliberation); and behaviour-based valuation (to identify values by observing the behaviour of individuals) (Pascual et al., 2023). It incorporates knowledge of NC valuation, developed at the James Hutton Institute (Nijnik and Miller, 2017) including in the project JHI-D5-1 (Martino et al., 2022), along with stakeholder perspectives elicited through expert consultation (Joyce et al., 2023) to define boundaries on values and valuation practices applied to woodland and forest ecosystems.

Following expert consultation (M3.1) and feedback received, including on prioritization of the gaps in NC valuation to be addressed, our approach was originally presented at a workshop in January 2024, organised within the remit of the RESAS JHI-D5-1 and JHI-D5-2 projects. It was discussed with researchers, policy makers, land and forest managers, operators of the forestry industry, and representatives of local communities. Foreseeable drivers and pressures affecting NC, and assumptions about how the development of these drivers could affect the condition and values of forest-based NC were explored through the development of scenarios, a particular module of our framework essential to producing a broad narrative that can be used to lead the development of NC under a specific context. The framework proposed in this report benefits from comments received during the workshop and by Scottish Government officers who reviewed a draft of this report. The framework has a general structure and can be tested on several NC assets and at different scales, although it is particularly adaptable at landscape and catchment levels where the management of land can be more easily addressed by bottom-up decision-making.

The framework is articulated in several modules to depict ecological, social, and economic values of NC. In addition, it suggests a range of methods for data collection and analysis, although a thorough investigation of tools in relation to their utility for capturing different values will be the subject of another report. Literature reviews, conducted by the research team (Martino et al., 2022; Martino et al., in review; Joyce et al., 2023), show that some of the most widely-used methods are based on deliberative and interpretive-deliberative approaches (e.g., digital storytelling, participatory video, GIS mapping), traditional economic valuation (e.g., contingent valuation and choice experiments), or psychometric-deliberative analyses (e.g., multicriteria analysis and Q-method) (Nijnik et al., 2013) to identify the diversity of existing discourses and inform the classification of groups of value.

Research from the IPBES (Pascual et al., 2023) showed that biophysical (nature-based) valuation methods have so far been applied the most, followed by statement-based, behaviour-based and integrated valuation methods. Instrumental values are elicited more often than intrinsic and relational values, although recently the last two have been profoundly analysed and their relationships and overlaps explored (Himes et al., 2023). These results explain the typologies of decision-making commonly implemented by land developers and NC users, based on pursuing a neoliberal utilitarian

approach to resource management, often contrary to the cultural needs of the communities that may be impacted by external decisions imposed for economic necessities. To change the way decisions are taken, it is necessary to extend the range of what we measure (De Valck et al., 2023) and consider the perspectives of a broader range of stakeholders. International evidence reports that 62% of nature-based valuation studies do not involve stakeholders' participation (Pascual et al., 2023) and less than 5% of published peer-reviewed valuation studies are used for informing decision-making (Barton et al., 2022).

To overcome the issues mentioned above, we propose a framework that brings a plurality of values into the valuation process and associated decision making and moves beyond the use of monetary values by technocratic approaches, such as traditional cost benefit analysis (CBA) (Turner et al., 2016; 2019). In addition, the framework delineates a process of knowledge co-creation (e.g., through participatory (GIS) mapping, deliberative valuation of management scenarios/policy alternatives), capturing systems' complexities and inter-connections.

To formulate our framework, we have taken into consideration the evolution of the international debate on ES and NC. Initial attempts at valuing nature addressed the diversity and quality of the ES provided by the environment (MEA, 2005), distinguishing them into provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural services. The MEA framework has evolved to consider merely the economic aspects of the above-mentioned ES through The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) initiative (TEEB, 2010), using a cascade model that from ecosystem functions conduces to the generation of ES and finally to the rise of wellbeing (Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011). More recently, the dialogue around the generation of ES has evolved to encompass the concept of NC, which can be defined as the stock and flow of both renewable and non-renewable natural resources (e.g., water, biodiversity, air) providing benefits to society (Bateman and Mace, 2020; Barbier, 2019;2022).

In the UK, observable links between ES, societal benefits, and wellbeing across a broad spectrum of ecosystems were described in the National Ecosystem Assessment (UK NEA, 2011). Cultural ES were addressed primarily in the UK NEA Follow On project (NEAFO, 2014). The NEAFO framework recognises the importance of NC for the provision of inspirational places essential for our individual and social wellbeing. A more recent categorisation of approaches, methods, and tools, tailored to specific value typologies, is provided by the UK Enabling Natural Capital Approach (ENCA) initiative (ENCA, 2023).

We decided to build our framework on the important contribution provided by the IPBES that recognises ES as Nature's Contribution to People (NCP) (Diaz et al., 2018; IBPES, 2018; 2019), addressing the need to consider local knowledge, influences, and implications of any policy decisions on cultures at the local level. Thus, the framework evaluates socio-cultural aspects related to NC and integrates them with more traditional approaches based on the analysis of monetary values. Work to clarify how this integration can occur is still an open debate (Burdon et al., 2022; De Valck et al., 2023) and requires stakeholders to be at the centre of the NC valuation process.

Finally, the framework encourages participants to discuss monetary and non-monetary values and the influence of different drivers upon NC, to formulate scenarios, and contextualise them locally by providing spatially bounded information on how participants aspire to use their landscape. Using observations gathered in workshops, the framework examines the potential for participatory mapping to capture socio-cultural values in a landscape context, and outlines how to integrate them with utilitarian values, along with the needs of deliberation to mitigate and manage contestation in the valuation and governance of NC (Kenter, 2016a; 2017; Martino et al., 2018).

Conceptual basis of the framework

Our work aligns with the IPBES (2022) conceptual valuation of nature that proposes a framework to understand relations between different values. According to Himes et al (2023), people perceive, experience, and interact with nature in many ways. This generates different understandings of the role that nature plays for their quality of life, leading to a wide diversity of values about nature.

However, policymaking largely disregards the multiple ways in which nature matters to people and prioritizes a narrow set of nature's values. Policies usually overlook the non-market values associated with nature contribution to people (NCP) (Diaz et al., 2018; IPBES, 2018; 2019), including the functions, structures, and ecosystem processes upon which life depends. Conversely, conservation policies that focus on intrinsic values of biodiversity may downplay relational values and exclude local populations that depend on nature for their livelihoods.

To capture these multiple values, it is necessary to explore the broad range of value perspectives that encompass people's relationships with nature. IPBES (2022), and Pascual et al. (2023) recognise that these relationships are complex and can be explored holistically, looking at different intertwined aspects that include:

- (i) *worldviews* - the ways in which people conceive and interact with the world. These can be considered as bodies of knowledge, practices, and beliefs such as academic, indigenous, and local knowledge systems;
- (ii) *broad values* - the moral principles and life goals that guide people-nature interactions;
- (iii) *specific values* - judgements regarding the importance of nature in particular contexts, grouped into:
 - a. instrumental values (i.e., means to a desired end often associated with the notion of ES);
 - b. relational values (i.e., the meaningfulness of human-nature interactions);
 - c. intrinsic values (i.e., the value of nature, independent of people); and
- (iv) *value indicators* - the quantitative measures and qualitative descriptors used to denote nature's importance in terms of biophysical, monetary, or socio-cultural metrics.

Specific values can be seen as embedded in broader overarching principles (broad values) informing our life, with worldviews providing a framework for these overarching principles shared by communities according to moral, cultural, and religious beliefs. Recognition of non-instrumental values (intrinsic and relational) is important for decision making. When values like stewardship are integrated, decision-making delivers more just and sustainable outcomes (Anderson et al., 2022).

Assessing broad values is important to formulate a transition in the framing of decision-making to a more balanced range of values, often not considered in political and economic decisions. This may reduce the dominance of those values that mostly relate to individualism and materialism and emanate from a market-based utilitarian view, whilst mobilizing relational, intrinsic, and non-market instrumental perspectives (Kenter et al., 2015; Kenter, 2016a; de Valck et al., 2023). In addition, considering broad values as an overarching or umbrella concept helps address how societal goals are aligned with general principles like justice, stewardship, unity, and responsibility, both towards other people and nature (Kenter, 2016; Kenter et al., 2016a; Sarkki et al., 2019a).

The IPBES (2022) values' perspective includes categories which are representative of the value systems of western scientific culture such as biodiversity, ecosystems (both structure and functioning), evolution, the biosphere and biocultural diversity. However, it pursues other knowledge systems, including categories such as Mother Earth and systems of life, where nature is viewed as

inextricably linked to humans, not seen as a separate entity. This view is more inclusive of the traditional ES definition given by environmental economists, such as the one formulated in the Dasgupta Review (Dasgupta, 2021) where nature is framed as an ‘asset to be managed’. Viewing nature simply as a pool of resources to be used more efficiently implies a sense of control over it, following the notion that an economic good or service exists only to be utilised and managed according to human need alone (Spash, 2021).

To operate in a more inclusive space, it is necessary to look at an approach that is based on the understanding of the socio-ecological system (Sarkki et al., 2017) through the analysis of key stakeholders’ roles, their relationships under scenario planning, and the valuation of these scenarios by a combination of approaches that build on economic valuation and social assessment (De Valck et al., 2023). Analysis of stakeholders’ values must reflect individualistic, professional, and collectivistic perspectives (preferences) of society and can be explored through a deliberative approach (Kenter et al., 2016b) to fully capture the “Total Social Value” (Burdon et al., 2019), a holistic measure of ecological and socio-cultural values, combined with more traditionally acknowledged economic worth. This approach could promote collaborative forest governance (Sarkki et al., 2019b; Melnykovich et al., 2019).

We follow the framework proposed by De Valck et al (2023) that incorporates the views of both individuals and society in the valuation of ES to be better aligned with the idea of “Total Social Value”. This framework suggests the adoption of the principles of ecosystem accounting for identifying uses, users, benefits, and values in a specific context, but at the same time, goes beyond biophysical and monetary accounting, also capturing the views of the human-nature system from a spiritual, cultural, and nature-centric perspective. For instance, De Valck et al (2023) describe the Australian Ewamian Aboriginal People of North Queensland as an integral part of complex, interconnected ecosystems and consider their stewardship of the environment as constituting a reciprocal relationship.

Importantly, in developing our valuation framework, we take inspiration from the triple balance sheet developed by Turner (2016) and combine socio-cultural values with the traditional “Total Economic Value” (TEV) framework (Richardson and Loomis, 2009), to achieve a more comprehensive analysis of “Total Social Value” (TSV) (Burdon et al., 2019). We do this because the TEV concept on its own is based on an economic vision of value (Nunes and van den Bergh 2001)¹ the biases of which have been extensively discussed in the literature (Bateman et al. 2010). In addition, the TEV concept is criticised for using figures, which are perceived as too abstract and indicative, while values are complex and dynamic. The use of TEV alone may also lead to double counting and risks of overstating the NC and ES values generated (Fisher et al., 2011), while in some cases the opposite can be observed.

To correct this by considering the importance of accounting for a plurality of values we refer also to the methodological work carried out by Nijnik and Miller (2017), and in empirical terms by Xu et al (2019) in China, van Kooten et al (2019) in Canada, and Nijnik et al (2017) in Ukraine. In Scotland, this is highlighted in a recent review of NC valuation with a focus on the forest and woodland context (Martino et al., 2022; Martino et al., in review), and from a stakeholder analysis of the perceived values of forests and woodlands (Joyce et al., 2023). Specifically, four main topics emerged from Joyce et al. (2023): 1) the importance of multiple views in the relationships between people and forests; 2) a recognition of the role of woodland as a multifunctional asset; 3) a recognition of the currently limited

¹ TEV provides an all-encompassing measure of the economic value of any environmental asset. It decomposes into use and non-use (or passive use) values. If a good has no market price, the consumer surplus (CS) is used to represent the TEV. CS is the difference between what an individual is willing to pay for a good or services and what he pays.

consideration of communities' values in NC valuation, as related to sense of place, cultural heritage, historic and archaeological features; 4) a recognition of the importance of stakeholders' participation in decision-making.

In real life situations, values vary among individuals and groups, and they change temporally and spatially. This creates complexity surrounding NC, exacerbated when it is unclear whether economic values represent a large share or a small fraction of the true TEV, for example, of unique and endangered ecosystems, which are near thresholds, meaning economic analysis alone will not be an appropriate solution (Nijnik and Miller, 2017). Given a range of uncertainties and potentially irreversible impacts of some decisions on certain types of ecosystems, and particularly on their intrinsic values, ethical and political choices should be made carefully. Value estimates should aim to address benefits enjoyed by the global community, such as wildlife protection or carbon sequestration as well as use values to local communities and people on the ground.

Therefore, NC valuation work should focus on advancing the TEV conceptualization by combining it with socio-cultural valuations and integrating it into decision making processes at various levels (Nijnik et al., 2011). This understanding has spurred scientists into inter- and trans-disciplinary working, with refined concepts arising from areas of environmental assessments to improve public policy in addressing UN Agenda 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (e.g. Daniel et al., 2012; Raymond et al., 2014). Thus, whether the aim is a more sustainable use of natural assets, knowledge exchange, or the facilitating of citizen actions, a framework which involves stakeholder participation needs to be adopted and adequately supported, enabling end-user and public awareness-raising, consistent with the UN Aarhus Convention (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 1998) and the provision of information on NC and ES values.

With this in mind, in the development of our framework, we combine social and economic valuation and rely on the co-construction of new knowledge with end-users. We do this by focussing on:

- 1) the NC-ES cascade model operationalised by the United Nations System of Environmental Economic Accounting - Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework, as proposed by Bateman and Mace (2020), to accompany the analysis of welfare, as measured by neoclassical economists (Pearce and Turner et al., 1989);
- 2) spatial and socio-economic analysis of stakeholder values, expressed as economic impacts (e.g., jobs) and cultural values (e.g., landscape, aesthetic, spiritual values, etc.) (Turner, 2016);
- 3) stakeholders' negotiation over contested issues on the values expressed at point 1 and 2 to support the implementation of solutions for policy and practice (Turner et al., 2019; Kenter et al., 2016b).

In particular, the first point addresses, according to the first balance sheet proposed by Turner (2016), the valuation of net economic benefits for the society (without considering distributional aspects). This approach aims to achieve the valuation of ES under different NC management scenarios using methods developed in neoclassical economics for the analysis of human preferences (Parks and Gowdy, 2013) such as CBA. The second point builds on the second balance sheet, concerning the identification of the major stakeholders in a given decision-making context, and their values, to reveal contested issues and potential conflicts between stakeholder groups (Martino et al., 2018). These values can be expressed in economic terms, focussing on the impacts of a policy such as jobs created, added value to the economy, etc., but they may more deeply address the cultural impacts of the policy to be implemented. Finally, the third point addresses the negotiation of contested issues (Hockley 2014; Turner et al., 2019), and supports the implementation of measures of compensation (in kind,

biodiversity, habitat offsets), as well as substitution of natural and social capitals with financial compensation. Deliberating on solutions that satisfy all parties requires understanding of the relevant views, motivations, and beliefs of all stakeholders.

Description of the framework

The framework depicted in Figure 1 contains all the features proposed in the previous section and links NC, ES, values, and wellbeing to end users. It is based on participatory processes that explore values, and tangentially provides some methods that could be useful for NC valuation, under scenario planning, to inform decision making at a landscape scale. The framework is modular, and each element is described in the next sections.

Figure 1: Framework for the methodological analysis of NC values.

The framework can be implemented operating from top to bottom. The upper part addresses the issues of what values and how these values can be used to discuss, under different drivers (social, technology, economy, environment, and policy), future scenarios for the NC of interest (for instance a forest or peatland). The discussion around the change in the NC under different scenarios is mediated by the set of values expressed in the valuing exercise. This specific panel can be used for the formulation of a new policy and to set a range of criteria or objectives for resource management that reflect the values a society is expected to generate from the implementation of that policy. The panel reported at the bottom of Figure 1 proposes a strategy to contextualise the scenarios emerging from the policy discussion proposed in the panel above, and to measure, by a participatory mapping approach, a range of values referring to the environmental, economic, and socio-cultural domains. The economic valuation can be implemented using the TEV framework to assess the benefits to society of certain decisions and can be used for policy appraisal (e.g. cost benefit analysis). Additional analysis, based on the NC accounting framework, can be used to get a sense of strong sustainability, exploring over space, and if possible, over time, the changes in the stock of resources and the flows of ES generated. Because under the NC accounting approach these ES are viewed as benefits produced by NC and measured using the market approach, they can be directly related to the value of economic activities; thus, they can be used to measure the economic impacts that NC generates on the economy. Finally, the socio-cultural values reflect the capacity of individuals to relate with the environment and show non-utilitarian perspectives. Because the three typologies of ecological, cultural, and economic values may diverge under different scenarios and may produce conflicts between stakeholders (in other terms trade-offs may emerge), it is recommended to have a final discussion based on deliberation over contested issues to decide on strategies that reduce the level of conflicts and generate the highest degree of satisfaction amongst stakeholders.

Value perception analysis

The first step of the approach consists of a preliminary analysis of the importance of different values and how these can be classified using the IPBES framework (2022) to fulfil societal and individual needs. For the aim of this project, this first step is exemplified by gathering experts and stakeholders' opinions on the values they elicit for forests and woodlands and their perceptions of the risks posed to forest-based NC by climate change. A detailed analysis of these values in the Scottish forest and woodland context is elaborated in Joyce et al. (2023a) and Joyce et al. (2023b). This step of the framework development can be also used to capture the positions that stakeholders have with regards to different *Life Frames* (IPBES, 2022; Kenter et al., 2022). Deliberation is used to capture values beyond narratives that prioritise only instrumental values, to better explore nature's capacity to provide resources for sustaining non-material livelihoods through recognition of relational and intrinsic values (Pascual et al., 2023).

Scenario planning

The second step of the framework is the discussion around the formulation of narrative scenarios that describe plausible future events, conditions and trajectories related to NC. Working with scenarios helps explore the social, technological, environmental, economic, and policy (STEEP) drivers that influence the condition and values of NC. Analysis of these scenarios can also help identify solutions to the threats posed to NC by the climate and biodiversity crises.

Relevant STEEP drivers of change can be discussed in focus groups, and their impacts on NC assets deliberated. Tools including the "morphological matrix" (Johansen, 2018) can be used by participants to aid formulation of the scenarios. This process involves listing a set of drivers (among the STEEP categories) to be reported in the first column of the matrix, and then deriving a set of assumptions, through deliberation, about how each driver could influence NC assets, in subsequent columns. The matrix should include a mixture of positive, 'business as usual', and negative assumptions for each driver. Combinations of these assumptions are used to create a set of narrative outlines that can be used to discuss impacts on NC extent and condition and implications for resource management (Duckett et al., 2022; Poskitt et al., 2024).

Exploring scenarios can be facilitated by the values elicited in the previous frame. For instance, describing those scenarios in which climate change is a driver is relevant to exploring and emphasising forest multifunctionality, with its biodiversity, recreational and aesthetic values, a sense of community, and others, beyond the commercial values traditionally elicited from forests (Nijnik et al., 2010; 2013; 2016). Furthermore, analysis of the scenarios could help identify solutions that usefully valorise a range of values associated with NC, such as reinvesting timber income in sustainable forest management, and reconfiguring the traditional timber industry to generate multiple forest services.

Scenario contextualisation

The third step of the framework depicts the scenarios within the social and ecological setting of a specific decision context. This is achieved by contextualising the overall narrative on NC in the landscape of interest through deliberation, resulting in a set of management strategies for the NC, which can help in exploring the robustness of policies and governance. Interpretive-deliberative methods, such as participatory mapping, storytelling coupled with deliberation, or arts-based dialogue (Kenter et al., 2015) (see for details next section and Table 1) can be used to collectively understand the interactions between stakeholders, measure the benefits that can be generated, and explore the relationships between cultural values (with special focus on relational and eco-centric values), and extent and condition of NC under different scenarios. The diversity of habitats, and of

the ES and biodiversity that NC sustains, provides inspiration, contemplation, and creation of cultural services as an essential support for individual and social wellbeing.

Scenarios for the management of NC can be analysed by ecological and economic modelling to measure welfare effects on society as proposed by Turner et al (2019), allowing the emergence of a broad range of instrumental (i.e., the value of other-than-human nature as means to an end - James 2020), intrinsic (emerging from something that is an end in itself; Berry et al., 2018; Piccolo, 2017), and relational values (arising from desirable, meaningful and reciprocal relationship with nature; Chan et al., 2016; Schröter et al., 2020). The approach we propose facilitates the emergence of a plurality of values related to biophysical, monetary, and cultural ES.

Natural Capital accounting and economic valuation

Economic values can be elicited by revealed and stated preferences to reflect an anthropocentric and instrumental perspective (i.e., as a means to achieve an objective), typical of neoclassical economics, schematised in the TEV framework (Anderson et al., 2022). Within this framework, the 'use' value refers to the benefits arising from a direct use of NC (e.g., timber, and non-timber forest products), and indirect uses such as regulating services of climate, soil retention, soil fertility and water quality, to mention a few. The 'non-use' value category, an expression of a dimension bridging instrumental and intrinsic valuation approaches (Hilmes et al, 2023) is bounded by the existence value concept and encompasses intragenerational altruism (i.e., wanting the asset/service to be maintained so others can use it), intergenerational altruism (bequest value, maintaining the service for future generations) and stewardship motivation (existence value, non-human resources generate benefits and/or interests simply through knowing they exist) (Pearce and Turner, 1989; Turner et al., 2019). The TEV can be applied to the NC and ES cascade illustrated in Figure 2 to value the benefits arising from a cascade model where NC is seen as the stock of resources that support functional processes such as primary productivity, water, and nutrient cycling, etc., which in turn sustain the generation of ES that underpin societal benefits.

Our framework emphasises the importance of complementing these utilitarian economic values with the SEEA-EA approach, the statistical standard designed by the UN Statistical Commission (UN, 2021). This approach is based on the consideration that any expression of the natural environment is a NC asset. Nature is not only an economic asset that contributes to the generation of wealth (Hache, 2019), according to capital theory developed by Hotelling (1931), but the foundation of functions sustaining our life. This has the advantage of answering more thoroughly the question "what is measured?" that is better addressed by exploring the extent of an ecosystem and its condition rather than the values of the ES generated (De Valck et al., 2023).

Following the SEEA-EA standard, three biophysical and two monetary accounts are suggested: 1) ecosystem extent (size) accounts; 2) ecosystem condition (quality) accounts; 3) ES flow accounts (expressed in physical terms); 4) ES flow accounts (expressed in monetary terms); and 5) monetary ecosystem asset accounts. This standard emphasises how to make an estimate of the biophysical extent of natural assets (accounts 1 and 2), while flows of ES proposed by the accounts (3) and (4) underpin benefits to society. Account (5) can be used to capitalise the ES generated by NC. To do that, it is necessary to introduce assumptions of the duration of the ES generated and the discount rate (HM Treasury Book, 2020). To limit the complexities of discounting (Nijnik and Pajot, 2014), it is suggested to refer to the physical aspects of NC (accounts 2 and 3) rather than to its monetary quantification.

In our framework, by extending the SEEA framework to the TEV, greater emphasis is placed on the sustaining of resource stocks not captured by traditional CBA operated according to the principles of weak sustainability (Nijnik, 2004) and assuming the possibility of infinite substitutability between

capitals (thus allowing benefits to be maintained if stocks of natural resources are replaced by other forms of capitals) (Helm, 2019).

The combination of stock of NC and functional processes produces a flow of ES, as schematised in the economic valuation frame reported at the bottom of Figure 1. Although ES have non-economic values in their own right, their value to humans arises in combination with the services provided by other capital assets, such as human, social, and manufactured, as proposed by Costanza et al. (2014). Benefits and contribution to human wellbeing cannot all be produced (especially provisioning and cultural values) without the input of human labour, energy, machinery, etc. (Bateman and Mace, 2020). There are several categorisations of ES that are also inter-related (e.g. regulatory services enhance provisioning services; putting too much emphasis on provisional services could result in undermining the cultural/social value of NC). The case of biodiversity is very special. It can be seen as a NC asset which maintains ecosystem functions (Cardinale et al., 2012), enhances productivity (Oliver et al., 2015), provides recreational benefits (Hausman et al., 2016) and generates non-use values (Pascual et al., 2011). Thus, biodiversity can be valued for its capacity of underpinning the provision of ES or can be seen as an ES in itself.

Socio-cultural valuation

The framework developed assesses socio-cultural aspects of NC to complement economic values. A range of proxy indicators are needed to identify these values because preferences expressed by a monetary indicator do not capture the full meaning of values related to intrinsic and relational aspects of nature (Anderson et al., 2022). We look at those entities expressed independently from any reference to people and human relationships with nature, as overarching moral principles and life goals that guide people-nature interactions and therefore are non-negotiable and non-tradable (Temper, 2019). Participatory mapping and GIS tools are increasingly considered best practice for eliciting non-instrumental values relating to the natural world by actively encouraging participants to include spatially bounded information about how and where they use nature, reinforcing cultural benefits associated with sense of place, wellbeing, and health (Burdon et al., 2019).

Deliberation of contested issues

The combination of economic analysis and social innovation is necessary to elicit the Total Social Value. This is informed by participatory deliberation of conflicting values, represented by the articulation of the socio-cultural aspects, ecological dimensions and monetary aspects associated with NC. This analysis demands further development of agreed principles which may in turn require deliberative approaches to help decision-makers choose among alternative options (Pascual et al., 2023). A graphical proposal, made by the quali-quantitative representation of all of these values, can be formulated through a discrete point-Likert scale (e.g., as high, medium, and low importance) (Potts et al., 2014; Burdon et al., 2022) or along a continuous 0 to 1 scale to visualise the main trade-offs between ES and deliberate on the selection of those scenarios that minimises conflicts.

Methods for implementing the different steps of the framework

There is a broad range of methods (Kenter et al., 2014; 2015) to analyse various dimensions of value. It is beyond the scope of this report to propose social science methods to study cultural values (or any other values), as this will be done in deliverable D2.2 of this project. Herewith, we focus mainly on some aspects of deliberation as a process towards agreeing on a plurality of values by consensus or majority vote, which are often poorly formed around complex environmental questions (Kenter et al., 2016a, b). In implementing the framework, we refer mainly to interpretive-deliberative methods that

link deliberation with qualitative, ethnographic, and sometimes arts-based approaches; and deliberative-psychometric approaches that combine group deliberation with psychometric indicators that seek to identify constructs such as different forms of values, discourses, or wellbeing. We plan to use a combination of approaches as proposed in Table 1.

Table 1: Examples of methods and tools planned for the implementation of the Framework.

Methods and techniques		Description
Economic	Stated preference methods	Participants are asked in surveys to express their willingness to pay for different aspects of nature that provide a cultural benefit (e.g., heritage value or place). The most common approaches are contingent valuation and choice experiments.
Deliberative	In-depth discussion groups	Group discussions (often repeated and usually involving four to eight people), during which participants shape the terms of the discussion, develop themes in ways relevant to their own needs and priorities.
Analytical–deliberative	Deliberative monetary valuation	Techniques that use formal methods of group deliberation to come to a decision on monetary values for environmental change. May be integrated with survey-based techniques (contingent valuation or choice experiments) or use a non-econometric approach to establish values (e.g., by incorporating citizens' juries).
	Deliberative multi-criteria analysis	Techniques that involve groups of stakeholders designing formal criteria against which to judge the non-monetary and (sometimes) monetary costs and benefits of different management options as the basis for deciding.
Interpretive–deliberative	Participatory mapping/GIS	A group of stakeholders considers or creates a physical or digital map to indicate landscape features that are valuable (and/or problematic). Participants may also rate or rank these features for importance. Map layers can also incorporate photo, video, artwork, poetry, etc.
	Storytelling	Participants are asked to tell stories about their experiences of or in relation to places. These may be reflected upon in a group setting to discuss values related to these experiences.
Psychometric–deliberative	Q-methodology	A method that organises qualitative statements that are evaluated and prioritised by respondents, either individually or through group deliberation. These are then analysed statistically to identify different discourses across the statements within the respondents group.

Sources: adapted from Kenter et al (2023)

The Q-methodology, a deliberative approach based on psychometric analysis (Pike et al., 2015; Simpson et al., 2016), is a relevant tool to systematise the stakeholders' viewpoints on value (Kenter and O'Connor, 2020) and investigate the perspectives of participants informed by different value stances (from utilitarian to pure eco-centric perspectives) (Nijnik et al., 2011; 2013). The methodology is suitable for reducing information, systematising point of views and revealing patterns between participant attitudes across a sample of variables. The focus is to capture the breadth and a variety of perspectives involving the analysis of approaches used to manage NC.

In addition, we plan to contextualise the generally framed scenarios through interpretive deliberative approaches such as participatory mapping, to capture spatially explicit data (Brown and Fagerholm, 2015) through stakeholders' deliberation. This approach can help enable more accurate spatial mapping of ecosystem uses and values on a local scale and can help facilitate the resolution of contested issues by providing a mechanism for conflict resolution (Burdon et al., 2019). The approach is also relevant for capturing non-tangible and subjective personal-spatial values of nature (e.g., sense of place, peacefulness, tranquillity) that are of limited understanding among many socio-cultural values (Klain and Chan, 2012; Brown and Fagerholm, 2015). In addition, this type of deliberative valuation may involve not just deliberating on information but also moralisation (Lo and Spash, 2012). Kenter et al. (2016b) argue that explicit pathways for reflecting on broad shared values are an essential component of robust deliberative value formation processes, given that environmental goods are often expressive of environmental values (Chan et al., 2012; Raymond and Kenter, 2016).

Community-based mapping is affirming as a process that offers decision makers the ability to design management grounded in a spatial understanding of the ecosystem, e.g., mapping can identify spatial variation in ES supply and value. However, there are not many exercises integrating cultural values with NC and ES (Raymond et al., 2009; Burdon et al., 2019; 2022). Elicitation of socio-cultural values can be achieved by using a mapping approach based on a 2D (Irvine et al., 2018) or 3D (Nijnik and Miller, 2017; Miller et al., 2006; 2009; Nijnik et al., 2011; Nijnik et al., 2013) dimensional analysis of the landscape. This approach is used to build real time maps of features and NC assets of the landscape of interest under different scenarios using aerial (Sagoe et al., 2021) or satellite (Burdon et al., 2019) images, and to deliberate how current and expected NC assets may deliver ES and social wellbeing to reduce conflicts.

We expect that the implementation of participatory GIS may help quantify not only the tangible presence of physical assets and regulating ES (Burdon et al., 2019; 2022), but also symbolic and spiritual ES (Irvine, 2018). Accounting for the influence of landscape features using an interactive GIS approach informs the links between people and their natural environment (McKinley et al., 2020), and paves the way for a more integrated geographical analysis that allows cultural ES to be fully integrated into land management decisions (Tew et al., 2019).

Integration is necessary to avoid the risk of a methodological divide in which conventional economic valuation techniques deal with utilitarian and productive services, whilst more deliberative and participatory methods deal with shared social and cultural ones, in isolation from each other (Kenter et al. 2016b). Thus, the framework can be used to emphasise the need for greater integration of valuation approaches. Participatory mapping, for example, is a flexible and adaptive approach that has the potential to interact with other methods including NC assets and monetary valuation (Burdon et al., 2022). It can be used to set the scene for understanding the nexus between ecological and economic values. The NC-ES relationships can be exemplified as a linear cascade, as proposed in Figure 2, that shows examples of NC assets and how these generate ES through the role of ecological functions. These ES can be used by society and embedded in our economic system to generate benefits. To make an example, the biomass produced in terrestrial (timber, crops, wildlife) can be used for generating provisioning services (crops, livestock, non-timber forest products) and recreational activities (gaming) that are exchanged on a market, while soil retention, coastal defence, water, and air purification, provide additional benefits that have a positive impact to our economy although not reflected in market prices. However, the latter ES can still be valued using welfare analysis approaches by eliciting people's willingness to pay in contingent valuation markets, or inferring their values from the analysis of market prices of those goods that are embedded to environmental goods.

We propose a mixed-method approach to carry out the analysis of NC and the expected ES under different scenarios. Stated preferences can be used to elicit NC values by asking people to express their willingness to pay for a change in policy scenario, while behaviour-based valuation can be used to identify how people value nature by observing their behaviour and practices (Martino and Kenter, 2023). Market prices, simulated markets and cost-based approaches can be used to assess exchange values, as a measure of value typically used in accounting (UN, 2021). Conversely, methods recognised and tested to assess socio-cultural values can be classified as:

- 1) deductive approaches, employed through large-scale questionnaires;
- 2) inductive approaches, where interviews (Bryce et al., 2016; Sagoe et al., 2021) or focus groups make use of creative tools (Edwards et al., 2016; Fish et al., 2016), such as photo elicitation, visual mapping (Burdon et al., 2019) and community voice (Ranger et al., 2016; Ainsworth et al., 2019), to elucidate social values.

A complete valuation must be based on a range of approaches to bring out a plurality of values such as cultural, shared, and social ones (Miller et al., 2009; Nijnik et al., 2013; 2017; Kenter, 2016; Turner et al., 2019) to be integrated with the more traditionally explored monetary values associated with NC (Kenter et al. 2016a).

Figure 2: Cascade model representing the formation and generation of ES and wellbeing from NC with suggested methods for the analysis of economic and social values (see also Table 1). Accounting is mainly used to assess stock of NC with analysis of its extent and quality (condition). Economic valuation can be made through accounting with reference to the priced natural asset and can be linked to national economic activities that depend on it. However, welfare analysis can be introduced to measure those benefits provided by ES that do not have a market but generate wellbeing (e.g., pollution reduction, contribution to health of green and blue spaces, etc.) through the use of stated or revealed approaches such as CVM (contingent valuation method); CE (choice experiment); TCM (travel cost method); HPM (hedonic price method).

Extending the framework to policy making

The framework proposed in Figure 1 can also be adopted for policy making formulation and evaluation. It can be used for scenario planning, including the business as usual scenario (a projection of the baseline in the future), to raise evidence-based knowledge addressing valuation of single resource policies (water, forest, peatlands, etc.), and produce cross-cutting development and environmental plans. These products may benefit from implementing the scenario planning approach, while other modules that drive to the contextualisation of NC valuation and to the deliberation of contested values may be bypassed if not considered relevant. The specific modules referring to the analysis of the site context (bottom panel in Figure 1) through the implementation of participatory mapping for the valuation of monetary and non-monetary values is less relevant and can be ignored for the formulation of a new policy.

In the implementation of a specific policy, under scenarios deliberated by national (or regional) stakeholders, the ample range of values proposed (biophysical, economic, and social) can be used to identify policy-relevant issues related to the management of NC. To address these issues, links can be made between the physical changes in ecosystems, and economic and social welfare functions (King et al., 2024). For instance, valuations were used in Australia to compare trade-offs between provisioning and regulating ES to inform information systems of forests and promote their sustainable management (Keith et al., 2019). The broad range of values measured through the analytical framework supports the assessment of ex-ante policy impacts whose consequences can be debated through deliberation, shifting the analysis towards the use of less technocratic, but more holistic and participatory approaches to minimise conflicts.

Moving to the implementation side of the policy, the whole framework can be used to discuss or assess the use of instruments necessary to achieve policy targets in terms of their economic, social, and environmental impact such as eco-compensation or payment for ecosystem services schemes (PES) (Ouyang et al. 2020). Finally, monitoring the effectiveness of a policy outcome can be achieved by providing indicators on progress towards targets as a distance from the agreed objectives.

The framework proposed goes beyond the standard use of NC accounting in decision making (De Valck et al., 2023) and policy making (King et al., 2024). If the welfare analysis and the accounting approach provided by the UN SEEA can relate NC to the condition of habitats and the generation of wellbeing (Figure 2), extending the valuation to the cultural benefits that NC generates provides a new dimension that policy makers usually ignore when dealing with traditional CBA. We refer to the making of policies and decisions building on incommensurable values such as sense of duty, identities, social norms, and cultural beliefs (Spash, 2006; Irvine et al., 2016) to support choices that are usually based only on economic metrics (Sagoff 1998; Kenter et al, 2016b; Isacs et al., 2023). Table 2 provides a very preliminary idea of how the framework can meet the needs for the NC Scottish policies, considering only two policies selected from a review of NC policies by the research team (Joyce et al., 2022).

Table 2: Example of policies and how these can benefit from the framework

Policy	Goal	Cycle stage of the policy	Contribution of the framework
Land use strategy 2021-2026	Develop Regional Land Use Framework by 2023.	Formulate policy response	The framework can be used to take a NC/ ecosystem approach to identify, at a landscape level, potential land use changes with positive climate and environmental impacts. For deeper analysis it is possible to use modelling and integrate Cost Benefit Analysis with socio-cultural values change under different landscape scenarios
Scotland's Forestry Strategy: 2019-2029 overview'	Emphasise the economic contribution of forestry, going beyond forest product markets analysis Provision of opportunities by forests and woodlands for people to engage in healthy activities, and improve their physical health	Implement policy and policy instruments	Identify which areas should be prioritised for afforestation and forest restoration by considering forest multiple ES (its use for outdoor recreation, clear air and water provision, renewable energy, etc. and biodiversity benefits delivered) and human health and well being

Conclusion

This report presents an analytical framework developed to integrate in a common strategy a plurality of values brought out by a mixed method approach for improving decision making. We think that the framework proposed may be beneficial to different audiences such as academics, decision makers and policy makers who want to implement it.

Although the framework will be tested on case studies where the most common NC assets are woodlands and forests with the presence of peatlands and agricultural land, it has a general structure and can be adopted to other landscapes and land uses. It is specifically tailored to work with stakeholders and communities at local scale where top-down policies can be supplemented by bottom-up views informed by customary rules or general practices accepted in a specific social context or community. Because the goal is to assess multiple values that extend beyond exclusively anthropocentric perspectives, the framework is designed to complement the TEV with a holistic vision, using participatory approaches to evaluate more detailed socio-cultural values. This approach generates a framework that explores relational values between humans and nature, satisfying the *Life Framework* proposed by Kenter et al (2022), and incorporated in the value framework proposed by

the IPBES (IPBES, 2022; Pascual et al., 2023), by sightseeing new perspectives where relations between humans and nature are framed by mutual and reciprocal respect.

The framework developed does not neglect the formulation and analysis of more traditional monetary values but recognises the incommensurability of multiple values and their impossibility to be reconciled using traditional CBA. The approach proposed complements the analysis of traditional values such as provisioning, regulating and cultural ES, formally elicited through stated and revealed approaches, with less anthropocentric aspects of NC where each member of the community builds a sense of non-predatory ownership and attains awareness of being steward of nature.

Although approaches based on multicriteria decisions can be used to combine a plurality of values that cannot be brought together using a common scale, it is possible to reduce the level of technocracy of the debate by coalescing these values through deliberation. Deliberative processes are becoming more common at local scale to support participants to think through and discuss values with each other, providing opportunities to enhance understanding of biodiversity and ecosystems through social learning. They give the chance to consider intrinsic values of nature alongside instrumental ones and provide a more effective way to integrate values into policy and practice on the ground. *“As such, the future of environmental valuation may be in a closer integration between economic and broader social science approaches, which will require a loosening of some of the epistemic, ethical, value, and rationality assumptions that neoclassical environmental economists have upheld so far”* (Martino and Kenter, 2023: 19).

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